

Turbulent heat transfer in caves: From benchmark simulations towards real world applications

by

Alexander H. Jarosch¹, Friedrich Obleitner²

¹ThetaFrame Solutions, Kufstein, Austria

²Institute of Atmospheric and Cryospheric Sciences, University of Innsbruck, Innsbruck, Austria

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¹*ThetaFrame Solutions, Kufstein, Austria*

²*Institute of Atmospheric and Cryospheric Sciences, University of Innsbruck, Innsbruck, Austria*

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1 Introduction

Caves are known from all continents, representing unique underground systems variably linked to surface processes above the caves. Modern cave science therefore involves a variety of research fields ranging from geological, geochemical, atmospheric to biological and cultural sciences. Major research efforts address their unique ecosystems (e.g. [Mammola et al., 2019](#)), paleoclimate information stored in speleothems ([Fairchild and Baker, 2012](#)) and cave ice ([Persoiu and Lauritzen, 2017](#)) and the importance of caves as prehistoric shelters ([Dublyansky et al., 2021](#)). Many caves worldwide gained substantial economic importance as show caves, whose sustainable development increasingly builds on scientifically based knowledge about these underground environments ([Cigna, 2016](#)).

Many cave phenomena are related to specific microclimatic conditions (e.g. the existence of ice) which are predominantly governed by temperature and air flow conditions within the cave system. Both are interrelated and depend on complex interactions with the outside. Investigating these conditions is still difficult on an experimental basis (remoteness, instrument constraints and operability) and the resulting lack of data hampers the development of a physically based understanding of cave phenomena and related processes. Numerical modelling of cave systems has great potential to fill respective knowledge gaps.

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) models are amongst the most advanced tools to study air flow and its dependence on thermal conditions in complex geometrical structures, as for example found in caves. Such CFD models can also treat the thermal interaction between ice and air, which is another important aspect of our work. While CFD models were extensively used to investigate fluid dynamics in cavity structures in a theoretical and engineering setting (e.g. the lid driven cavity problem), only few publications address the application of CFD-models to complex cave-like structures (e.g. [Flores et al., 2013](#); [Yang and Shi, 2015](#); [Bertozzi et al., 2019](#)). These studies demonstrated a great potential of using CFD models in cave research. However generalizations and broad validity of these published findings remains difficult as the presented case studies focused on flow conditions in single caves subject to very specific external forcings.

Thus motivated, we employ CFD models to simulate air flow and temperature in idealized sag-type cave structures. First, we simplify the geometry of an ice-bearing cave in the Austrian Alps. Second, we constrain the overwhelming variability of natural outside temperature and wind configurations, which is a current focus of comprehensive micrometeorological investigations, to typical summer- and wintertime conditions observed at this Alpine cave site. Thermal wall boundary conditions in our cave simulations are also taken from respective observational data. Process-wise, we treat coupled aerodynamic and thermal processes, however neglecting the influences of radiation, latent heat exchange and thermal conduction in wall regions. Overall we perform parameter studies on the structural sensitivity of air flow, with complexity progressively approaching „real“ conditions i.e., observational data.

This report summarizes our current effort towards physically-based modelling of air circulation and thermal conditions in sag-type cave environments containing ice, with a focus on model performance evaluation. We further introduce results from a first set of simulations referring to a simplified, yet cave-scale geometry which resembles the gross structure of the studied Alpine cave. These steps provide the basis for more detailed studies in the future.

2 Numerical model

For our simulations of turbulent air flow including thermodynamics within cave environments we employ OpenFOAM¹, which is a state of the art open-source and CFD modelling suite. The software provides a set of standard solvers to simulate complex fluid flow incl. turbulence, heat transfer, chemical reactions, acoustics, solid mechanics and electromagnetics. Discretisation of the governing equations is done with finite volumes. OpenFOAM has been validated by application to laboratory benchmark problems (e.g. Inok et al., 2013; Limane et al., 2014) and outdoor problems (e.g. Flores et al., 2013, 2014; Vuorinen et al., 2015; Balogh et al., 2012).

Two simulation series are performed which essentially represent mixed-convection fluid dynamic problems and are set up following best practise guidance (e.g. Rong et al., 2016). Simulations with model A aim at reproducing an indoor environment benchmark test (Nielsen, 1974) to demonstrate model performance. Having shown that, a second set of simulations (model B) is performed in order to study air flow and thermal conditions in an abstracted sag-type cave structure.

2.1 Model configuration

Some basic material specifications are common to all simulations (all referring to air @ 20°C and SI-units): reference density=1.204 kg m⁻³ (except in the buoyant force term i.e., Boussinesq approximation), incompressible, specific heat capacity = 717 J kg⁻¹ K⁻¹, dynamic viscosity = 1e⁻⁵ Pa s, thermal expansion coefficient = 3.43e-03 m m⁻¹ K⁻¹, Prandtl Number = 0.7. Table 1 shows the basic outline of model specifications, which are described in the following paragraphs.

2.2 Numerical solvers

Forced convection in cave structures which transports thermal energy requires appropriate numerical treatment. OpenFOAM offers several solvers which are able to resolve all physical processes relevant for our scenarios, namely conservation of mass, momentum and energy (heat) and integrated turbulence models. We choose *buoyantPimpleFoam* for this purpose, which is appropriate for transient simulations and can be configured to treat buoyancy effect based on the Boussinesq-approximation. This choice is supported by Limane et al. (2014) who also demonstrated that specification of the turbulent model had a strong impact on the accuracy of the simulation results. Their study corresponds geometry-wise with our Model A problem and it has been demonstrated that optimum model performance can be achieved by using a Reynolds-Averages Navier-Stokes (RANS) k- ϵ closure model. Our turbulent model choices are listed in Table 1. The second set of simulations we perform (cf. 2.3.2 below) utilizes a Wall-Adapting Local Eddy-viscosity (WALE) turbulent model and Large Eddy Simulations (LES), which should compute the correct wall asymptotic behavior for wall-bounded flows such as found in caves.

2.3 Boundary and initial conditions

2.3.1 Model A

Our aim is to reproduce flow and thermal conditions as observed by Nielsen (1974) where several Reynolds number regimes have been presented. As we also model natural caves, we focus on the low Reynolds number (Re) case with Re=4700 and use the same coordinate system, nomenclature, and dimensions as in the original publication. Corresponding inflow air velocity has not been explicitly defined in Nielsen (1974), however can be reconstructed by knowing the inlet height ($h = 0.007112$ m with $h/H = 0.056$) and the Reynolds Number to be $u_{\text{inlet}} = 5.4888$ m s⁻¹ at our reference temperature of 20°C, which we also use as the inflow air temperature. Turbulence intensity at the inlet is prescribed as 5%. Constant pressure conditions are set at the outflow (Table 1). The cavity walls are characterized by no-slip boundary conditions for velocity and as adiabatic except for the bottom, where a constant heat flux density is imposed. The heat flux (q) with which the bottom of the cavity is heated is also not explicitly stated. However we can reconstruct it to match the corresponding Archimedes numbers given by Nielsen (1974) (Ar ranging from $3.7e^{-6}$ to $1e^{-5}$) to be $q = 10$ W m².

¹Version 9 at <https://www.openfoam.org>

2.3.2 Model B

In this model we study coupled flow and heat transport in a cave geometry, which is abstracted from observations in a cavity-type cave containing perennial ice (Hundsalm ice cave, Austria). The sketched model geometry (cf. Table 1) resembles an open rectangular cavity with two upper entrances on the same spatial scale as the Hundsalm cave. For this initial run, which serves as a reference for subsequent sensitivity studies, inflow is characterized by a logarithmic wind profile which at a height of 2 m above ground has an average horizontal velocity with of 1 m s^{-1} . Inflow air temperature has a constant temperature of $+10^\circ\text{C}$ (summer case) and -10°C (winter case). Outflow is characterized by constant pressure conditions. The cavity walls have no-slip velocity boundary condition and are adiabatic, except for the bottom of the cave, which is set to 0°C in order to mimic the existence of ice in the cave. Our inlet velocity profile is determined from a spin-up run of a free atmospheric flow lasting 1200 seconds and the resulting velocity profile is calculated by averaging over 300 seconds.

3 Results

3.1 Model A

We reproduced the benchmark data from (Nielsen, 1974) with two different grid resolutions. In both cases we used the configuration described above (cf. 2.3.1), however with a nominal resolution of $dx = 0.0063$ and $dx = 0.0042$ m. Results from both runs are displayed in Figure 1 where we compare the simulated horizontal velocity profiles with the available benchmark data (cf. Fig. 2.4.5-1 in Nielsen (1974)). In Figure 2 we show the temperature profiles computed with our model in comparison to the benchmark data (cf. Fig 2.5-2 in Nielsen (1974)).

3.2 Model B

To demonstrate the capabilities of our model setup for simulating thermal transport in caves we showcase two typical seasonal scenarios (see configuration above 2.3.2).

In Figures 3 – 6 we display temperature and air flow results in the cave for summer conditions. Figures 7 – 10 show the same configuration for winter conditions. Animations of both cases can be found online²

4 Conclusion

To validate our model setup, we numerically reproduced a well-known CFD benchmark for forced convection in a cavity (Nielsen, 1974). In section 3.1 we demonstrated our numerical results to be in good agreement with the benchmark data for different grid resolutions.

As a showcase of our ongoing research on thermodynamics and air flow in naturally occurring cave structures, we presented initial results of numerical simulations on real cave scales. These simulations exhibit great potential to advance our understanding of heat exchange processes between caves and the outside atmosphere. Upcoming results will be published in peer-reviewed literature.

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²<https://vimeo.com/671126421> and <https://vimeo.com/671130786>

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	model A	model B
geometry		
represents	lab model (Nielsen, 1974)	abstracted sag-type cave geometry with bottom ice (Spötl et al., 2013, Fig. 1)
dimensions (X, Y, Z)	0.381 x 0.5969 x 0.127 m	90 x 30 x 35 m
mesh type	3D, hexahedral	3D, hexahedral
mesh resolution	0.0063 and 0.0042 m	0.25 m
number of grid cells	112800 and 380700	1093707
physics problem	mixed convection	mixed convection
wall conditions	no slip, adiabatic, bottom constant heat flux	no slip, adiabatic, bottom constant temperature
inlet conditions	constant velocity, constant temperature, zero pressure gradient	constant velocity, constant temperature, zero pressure gradient
outlet conditions	constant pressure, zero velocity gradient	constant pressure, zero velocity gradient
turbulence regime	Re = 4700	Re $\approx 1e^5$ (at cave entry)
turbulence model	RANS (k- ϵ)	LES (WALE)
OpenFOAM solver	buoyantPimpleFoam	buoyantPimpleFoam
Equation of state	Boussinesq	Boussinesq

Table 1: Basic configuration of simulation series A and B

Figure 1: Horizontal air speed for two model resolutions in comparison with benchmark data (Nielsen, 1974) at Re = 4700. Non-dimensionalization of the numerical results is done in accordance to the benchmark.

Figure 2: Along-flow temperature profiles for two model resolutions in comparison with benchmark data (Nielsen, 1974) at Re = 4700. Non-dimensionalization of the numerical results is done in accordance to the benchmark.

Figure 3: Model B at t=100 seconds for summertime conditions (inflow air temperature +10°C) over time. Upper cross-sections displays velocity magnitude and lower cross-sections temperature.

Figure 4: Model B at t=300 seconds for summertime conditions (inflow air temperature +10°C) over time. Upper cross-sections displays velocity magnitude and lower cross-sections temperature.

Figure 5: Model B at t=600 seconds for summertime conditions (inflow air temperature +10°C) over time. Upper cross-sections displays velocity magnitude and lower cross-sections temperature.

Figure 6: Model B at t=900 seconds for summertime conditions (inflow air temperature +10°C) over time. Upper cross-sections displays velocity magnitude and lower cross-sections temperature.

Figure 7: Model B at t=100 seconds for wintertime conditions (inflow air temperature -10°C) over time. Upper cross-sections displays velocity magnitude and lower cross-sections temperature.

Figure 8: Model B at t=300 seconds for wintertime conditions (inflow air temperature -10°C) over time. Upper cross-sections displays velocity magnitude and lower cross-sections temperature.

Figure 9: Model B at t=600 seconds for wintertime conditions (inflow air temperature -10°C) over time. Upper cross-sections displays velocity magnitude and lower cross-sections temperature.

Figure 10: Model B at t=900 seconds for wintertime conditions (inflow air temperature -10°C) over time. Upper cross-sections displays velocity magnitude and lower cross-sections temperature.